

The importance of soft skills in Entrepreneurship: a matter of acculturation

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Abstract: It is not complete to talk about Entrepreneurship, nor even about Education, without concerning the soft skills of each entrepreneur - what they know and what they learn from their own life and work experience. This article continues the study of late motivations of eighty entrepreneurs in Algarve territory. Using a qualitative methodology, evidence is collected from different people, with different cultures, about their soft knowledge in their enterprises. Different characteristics -skills- were found in the results, whose entrepreneurs from different territories and clearly different cultures. It can be concluded the importance of the Culture and soft skills: they influence the Entrepreneurship Education of these people. So, it is collected in this paper, local culture from different people, and it can be reflected that when they share in the same territory their experiences, they enrich them with more entrepreneurial skills. That kind of soft skills had been observed from this empiric results, and they can be useful to build a strongly Education for Entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education; Culture; Soft Skills

1. Introduction

When the phenomenon is Entrepreneurship, it is reflecting about people and their abilities, not only about enterprise numbers. In a sociological perspective, the importance of people experience cannot be ignored [1; 2; 3, 4].

Based on a complementary study [2] carried out in Algarve context, about women entrepreneurship, this article provides new insights into the role of education.

This introduction characterizes the context from Algarve territory, the focus of this research.

The Algarve has a strong Arab presence, which is still evident today, such as in the construction of typical houses with terraces (rooftops) where rainfall is scarce. The region relies on cisterns and whitewashed walls that reflect the sun, making the homes cooler. The Arab people transmitted the knowledge of adapting to the climate. Additionally, they developed artisanal artefacts, including Algarve chimneys, carpets, mills, and constructions related to water such as nora, picota, levada, dam, tank, cistern, and watermill, which facilitated agriculture. New irrigation techniques expanded production and introduced previously unknown crops, including orange trees, lemon trees, almond trees, fig trees, carob trees, olive trees, vines, and rice, among others. With the development of the primary sector and the construction of robust boats, the secondary sector, namely trade, also experienced limited growth for economic development in the region. This brief historical allusion [14] helps to understand not only the legacy left in labor matters but also to assess the region's long-standing identity of hospitality, which is devoted to a constant mixing of cultures, not only in the past but also in the present.

The Algarve region is divided into sixteen councils and two regions: Barlavento (west) and Sotavento (east) based on demography and economic position. According to a demographic study, the Algarve region accounts for less than 5% of the total population of Portugal [16]. However, during the summer season, there is a significant increase in

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population, which may require readjustment in social and collective structures, as well as an increase in the availability of products and services [15].

However, the migratory phenomenon in this region is considered atypical because the migrant population found does not fit the vulnerability patterns that are commonly studied in this field [17, 18]. The population of migrants from the United Kingdom is the largest in the Algarve region, with 17,230 English residents across Portugal, of which 10,045 live in this area. This makes it the largest demographic proportion of this nationality [16]. The towns of Loulé, Lagos, and Albufeira have the highest concentration of English residents in the region, with the so-called golden triangle located in Loulé, specifically in Quinta do Lago and Almancil.

Nevertheless, the region remains underdeveloped economically. The tourism industry dominates the services sector, leading to high unemployment rates that are worsened by strong seasonality [15]. In order to diversify the sectors of activity, it is necessary to have people with different skills.

From a social and cultural perspective, the Algarve is one of the most well-known regions in Portugal. Its international reputation is based on its mild climate throughout most of the year, the diverse beauty of its beaches, and more recently, its golf courses [15]. However, these are not the only resources that this ecosystem offers. In this small territory, there is potential for exploration in all geographical areas, including the north and south, interior and coast, and windward and leeward regions. This is particularly important to eliminate the stigma of peripherality that falls on less populated and explored places. It is important to note that there is still much to discover, especially from the perspective of migrant populations.

According to the demography statistics [16], this region is the most multicultural and intercultural. This suggests that the region has a higher number of inhabitants from different countries, and the locals are more accepting of this phenomenon. They quickly learn the behaviors and cultures of migrants [4].

It's observed that the region requires development and strong policies to promote entrepreneurship [5]. In 2022, Universidade do Algarve signed a memorandum with various local entities to promote entrepreneurial activities and internationalize a new brand called 'Algarve Tech Hub' [19]. Additionally, they started promoting the Algarve Web Summit festival [20].

Reflecting on the problem of entrepreneurial skills, entrepreneurship is a complex issue due to its eclectic nature. The mainstream view often confuses it with managing a company, but it is much more than that.

However, it does not solely begin or end with economic positions. Sociology focuses on human behaviors in groups. Its tools allow for the distinction between the entrepreneur stage and the businessman stage. Here, the entrepreneur is defined as the agent who creates something innovative, while the businessman manages an already established business. Therefore, it becomes a need to identify entrepreneurial skills.

When reviewing the literature, it is important to understand the concept of soft skills and their significance in relation to entrepreneurship.

The dichotomy between hard and soft skills, and the difference between what is learned in school versus through practical experience, is particularly relevant [7] due to the complexity of the characteristics of entrepreneurship. There are multiple classifications of what constitutes an entrepreneur [8, 9, 10, 11, 12]. However, none of them suggest that one can become an entrepreneur solely through academic learning. Therefore, it is a significant challenge to comprehend the concept and apply it to educational purposes. As per Dolabela [1], an entrepreneur must not overlook their life experiences and practical learning in their journey to becoming an entrepreneur. From this perspective, it can be understood that people are capable of learning. Additionally, people have ontological memories from their childhood that are relevant to their future. Entrepreneurial culture

often stems from direct observation of family and friends, as well as the social context in which they live. Living in a territory that promotes entrepreneurial activities can also contribute to this culture.

According to Jardim [5], the priority here is the relationship between culture, territory, and entrepreneurial practices.

Following Weberian classic structures [13], an entrepreneur is someone who has the autonomy to make their own decisions. By expanding the definition of entrepreneurship within the field of sociology, it is possible to consider broader analytical perspectives that may be overlooked in the fields of management or economics, which tend to focus more exclusively on quantitative methodologies.

This analysis connects the concept of culture to entrepreneurship.

Culture is directly associated with policing territories. Culture refers to the values that are shared by a community, shaping their behaviour, expectations, and even their interpretation of the world around them.

This research focuses on migrant women entrepreneurs from different nationalities who share the decision to start a business in a particular territory. The question is, what have they brought to this place?

This article aims to highlight the significance of soft skills and diverse cultures in promoting entrepreneurial activities in the Algarve region.

The research analyses the social and cultural impact of international entrepreneurs on the local community of Algarve, as well as their motivations for choosing this territory. As Jardim [5] reflects, it is useful to understand local policies and ecosystems in order to replicate them in other localities. It is also helpful [6] to prepare oneself when deciding to migrate to another country with a different culture. With this information, it becomes possible to develop educational programs based on real experiences to promote entrepreneurship education.

These entrepreneurs bring a different entrepreneurial culture and, of course, different perspectives on life, which means different experiences and knowledge. This is identified as soft skills.

2. Materials and Methods

This paper is based on the epistemological foundations of qualitative methodology [21, 22]. It includes eighty interviews with entrepreneurs from various nationalities, such as England, France, the Netherlands, Finland, Germany, and others. In addition, direct empirical observations were conducted and recorded using a recording device to accurately capture and translate the information.

To conduct a content analysis of these interviews, the research encountered difficulties in creating simple analysis tables due to the extensive content. This allowed for more precise formatting of the responses without losing any content. Therefore, the results were presented in a matrix and the data were processed using Maxqda software version 12 [23].

The transition from empirical to scientific knowledge involves compiling empirical data collected at the theoretical-conceptual level and using the same theories to interpret what is learned in the field through an epistemological process. It is important to note that there should be no gap between these processes so that empirical knowledge can lead to scientific knowledge [24].

In fieldwork or participant observation, the researcher must gain the trust of the object of study. By immersing themselves in the context, they can better understand why certain people act in a certain way. However, it is important to maintain methodological rigor and impartiality in the analytical approach.

This research involves observation, categorization, hypothesis induction, experimentation, and theoretical confrontation [24].

Given that entrepreneurship is not a science [26] and is eclectic in its study, it can be argued that creating epistemologies for entrepreneurship education is only possible if the researcher and educator have a deep understanding of the culture that biases an entrepreneur, as well as their territory. Therefore, it can be postulated that motivation can generate new entrepreneurs.

3. Results

To analyze the empirical results, a strategic framework was constructed that segmented and grouped similar information.

Eight parameters for analysis were identified:

- 1- The age which they begin in Algarve territory.
- 2- Childhood Dream
- 3- The family or other examples in childhood
- 4- Motivations and experiences
- 5- Why choose this territory
- 6- Territory Obstacles
- 7- Discussing Happiness
- 8- Opinions about Academy's intervention for Entrepreneurship

3.1. Age in beginning entrepreneurial activity in a new territory -Algarve

Figure 1

The table shows that the majority of the eighty entrepreneurs began their activities in the Algarve region at a young age, between thirty and thirty-nine years old. It is important to note that this population is made up of migrants to the region, so the data collected pertains specifically to their age when starting entrepreneurial activities in the Algarve, rather than in their overall life.

3.2. Childhood dream

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Figure 2

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Regarding ontology, it is analysed that the individuals have an entrepreneurial mindset. Their childhood and life experiences are also relevant in understanding why they have this dream. The culture and knowledge they have acquired may have influenced this.

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3.3. Examples in Childhood (family or friends)

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Figure 3

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Figure 2 shows that they have aspired to be entrepreneurs since childhood. Additionally, Figure 3 illustrates that they have been influenced by other entrepreneurs in their lives. This suggests that they prioritize learning from other successful entrepreneurs, which in turn motivates them to pursue their own entrepreneurial goals.

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3.4. Motivations

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Figure 4

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The table displays various motivations to become an entrepreneur, being the most common is to have a childhood dream of starting their own business and had prior experience in the field. Additionally, family members served as examples.

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3.5. Why choose this Territory

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Figure 5

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Due to these results, many migrant entrepreneurs come to the Algarve because it offers a high quality of life. Others come because they already have friends and family in the area, creating a sense of community.

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3.6. Obstacles in this Territory

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Figure 6

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The results revisit the same issues previously discussed regarding the Algarve territory, such as seasonality, the distant location of decision centres, and excessive bureaucracy. However, in comparison to the literature [11, 12, 15], this is a nationwide problem in Portugal. It is important to note that the Algarve is a peripheral location and therefore more vulnerable.

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3.7. If they are happy and want to go further

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Figure 7

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Upon analysis of their satisfaction level, it is evident that they wish to continue developing this territory through their entrepreneurial activities.

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3.8. Experience versus /Opinions about Academy

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Figure 8

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It can be observed that some entrepreneurs do not believe that academic fields can help them develop their activities. However, others are breaking stereotypes and are open to collaborating with academia to improve their entrepreneurial activities, especially in matters of innovation.

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4. Conceptual Discussion

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When comparing the empirical results with the literature consulted, similarities were noticed in the proposed skills. Entrepreneurs possess abilities that they have learned through observation since childhood.

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However, there was a difference found when compared to other literature on migration [17, 18]. The individuals interviewed for this research are entrepreneurs who migrated to Algarve to establish their enterprises, bringing with them certain conditions. As per the literature review, most migrants come to Algarve to enjoy their retirement, while others are vulnerable and seeking a better financial life. However, this article focuses on entrepreneurial skills and culture.

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Based on a review of the literature and observations of the cases in this study, three theorems can be proposed for discussion. These results are consistent with previous works published [4, 5, 6].

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Theorem 1: states that an entrepreneur typically has a childhood background,

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This is supported not only by this case study but also by others cited research [3, 5, 8, 9, 10]. However, it is important to note that this is a generalization and cannot be applied

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universally. This article presents a case study of two French twin sisters, both with the same financial situation provided by their parents, education, culture, and learning tools since childhood, who followed similar paths in the food sector. However, one sister succeeded while the other did not. The successful entrepreneur attributed her sister's lack of vision regarding the time and place to open the business as the reason for her failure. The management lacks strategic concentration.

In addition to childhood background, organization is important, which can often be achieved through discipline, learning, resilience, and good conduct.

Theorem 2. To motivate new entrepreneurs, the Educator can't ignore the importance of entrepreneurial soft skills.

There's no way to be an entrepreneur learning only by the school. In this paper it is revealed that entrepreneurs charge experience on the matter that is impossible to ignore, so, educators must collect that experience to motivate other new entrepreneurs in their respective fields.

Theorem 3. The culture of the territories its relevant to motivate new entrepreneurs.

The practice of entrepreneurial activities is closely related to the culture of the territory. According to Hofstede [6], it is advisable for anyone wishing to conduct business in other countries to consider the theory of cultural dimensions. This is because individuals already carry their cultural identity with them and may encounter or be surprised by new values from other cultures. It is important to use diversity as an advantage in the work context and in entrepreneurship. Understanding the culture of another country can provide a healthy competitive advantage by promoting openness, respect, and the use of differences as a valuable skill. This knowledge is essential for success when entering a new cultural environment. Additionally, familiarity with the local culture can aid educators in promoting entrepreneurship within the community [5].

The question of how to teach entrepreneurship has been the subject of much debate. When education is not instilled from an early age, the challenge of educating adults arises. Monteiro [25] argues that adult education encompasses new qualifications and mainly focuses on developing new technical skills. This education not only serves professional purposes related to work but also fulfills the requirements for the transformation and emancipation of citizens.

An important milestone in this analysis is to raise awareness about entrepreneurship education. According to Sarkar [9], this practice should be promoted as early as pre-primary education, where the individual's first foundations are formed. In an academic context, it is important to teach for entrepreneurship and not about entrepreneurship. Please note that 'for' and 'about' in the presented scenario, translate different paradigms in the field of education.

Therefore, this is a cultural issue. Societal policies should focus on providing resources and education to ensure a sustainable and secure future livelihood. The purpose of teaching entrepreneurship is to inspire individuals to utilize their potential, encourage reflection, and identify opportunities.

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5. Conclusions

This text problematizes the introduction of entrepreneurship programs into academic settings.

Currently, there are numerous didactic proposals being polarized in a multidisciplinary way, particularly in the fields of Management and Economics, but also in Sociology and other disciplinary branches. However, the challenge lies in bringing together a cohesive theoretical framework, as methods and techniques for teaching the phenomenon are dispersed. According to Filion's [27] theory, entrepreneurship cannot exist without practice. No changes in content have been made. Therefore, anyone who aims to teach it must possess practical experience, or 'know-how', in addition to theoretical knowledge. This highlights the importance of combining the concept of entrepreneurship with its practical application. The text has been edited to adhere to the desired characteristics of objectivity, comprehensibility, conventional structure, clear and objective language, format, formal register, structure, balance, precise word choice, and grammatical correctness. Another approach is to encourage entrepreneurship by leveraging the educator's knowledge and understanding of public policies and the economy of the region.

As Filion [27], entrepreneurship involves lifelong learning, which is based on the accumulated experience of the entrepreneur and the development of so-called transversal skills.

Entrepreneurship thus contributes to the eclipse of traditional teaching paradigms, breaking unilateral dogmatism and opening doors to new teaching methods that are based on enabling students to reflect for themselves, to develop their potential and autonomy, in a heuristic model produced for a framework of paradigmatic objectives. This would be the roadmap to a new scientific domain.

In this framework it's clearly observed, in literature and proven in this research, that each person's life story influences their cognitive capacity for the world, their way of interacting socially and solving problems. After collecting the empirical data, it was found similarities that bring each of the interviewees closer together, whether in terms of family, education, circle of friends, among other factors that contribute to human knowledge and entrepreneurial attitude. It also becomes aware of the multiplicity of elements that convey the agents' cognitive construction, between local and global involvements, between the connection of past and present experiences that are only understandable in individual analysis, in the person-context relationship of each discourse.

Regarding social development, the relevant structures focus on constructing and sharing knowledge made possible by interculturality in the area. An open society, aware of knowledge without borders and resource usage, moves towards development.

The entrepreneurial activities in this territory bring about various entrepreneurial visions regarding the region's resources and new demands arising from different consumption and service customs. However, it is important to note that the study was limited to only eighty interviews and there is a need to demystify entrepreneurship in local cultures to promote a more evolved society.

This article contributes to improving the conception of the state of the art in Entrepreneurship, changing its integration, with an interpretative position based on domains of Sociology, whose focus is human behavior. In this matter, soft skills are inseparable from the Entrepreneur's profile. Furthermore, territorial cultures are conditions for attracting or not new developments and entrepreneurial activities.

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